

References

1. P. S. FERNANDES and V. V. NADKARNY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 1059.
2. P. S. FERNANDES, V. V. NADKARNY, G. A. JABBAR and R. P. JANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 840.
3. K. C. JOSHI and D. S. NEHTA, *J. Indian, Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 613.
4. R. CREMLYN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968 (c), 11.
5. M. SHAH, C. T. BHATT and D. D. KANGA, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1375.
6. P. S. FERNANDES, R. D' COSTA and V. V. NADKARNY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 738.

Chemical Constituents of *Polypodium amoenum* Wall

ASOK DASGUPTA and H. N. KHASTGIR*

Department of Chemistry,

University of North Bengal, Darjeeling

Manuscript received 16 July 1977, revised 18 October 1977,

accepted 21 November 1977

POLYPODIUM amoenum (Polypodiaceae) grow in the Himalayan region at an altitude 4,000-11,000 ft and also from Garhwal to Bhutan, very common in Khasia range (altitude 3,000-6,000 ft). The present communication describes the isolation of fern-9(11)-ene²⁻³, hop-22(29)-ene⁴⁻⁶ and β -sitosterol from the whole plant.

Benzene extract of the dried powdered fern was separated into acid and neutral fractions. The latter was chromatographed over alumina. Elution with petrol (60-80°) yielded a waxy solid which was found by TLC (12% AgNO₃ impregnated silicagel) to be a mixture of two components. On rechromatography over silicagel (E. Merck) impregnated with AgNO₃ followed by crystallisation (chloroform : methanol) it afforded two hydrocarbons A and B having the same mol. formula C₃₀H₅₀(M⁺410).

Compound A (found C, 88.01, H, 12.15) m.p. 166-68° [α_D] CHCl₃ - 16.1° showed significant peaks at m/e 257, 243, 231 in its mass spectrum similar to those recorded for fern-9(11)-ene. Its identity was established by comparison with an authentic sample (m.m.p, IR and Co-TLC).

Compound B (found C, 87.59, H, 12.42), m.p. 210-11°, [α_D] CHCl₃ + 61°. $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 880 cm⁻¹ (>C=CH₂) was found to be identical (m.m.p, IR, MS) with hop-22(29)-ene (Diploptene).

Further elution of the column with petrol : benzene (3 : 2) furnished β -sitosterol, m.p. 133-36°, [α_D] CHCl₃ - 32°, acetate, m.p. 126-28°, [α_D] CHCl₃ - 38°, identical with authentic specimens.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Prof. G. Berti, University di Pisa, Italy for the authentic specimen of fern-9(11)-ene and to Dr. B. C. Das, CNRS, Gif-Sur-Yvette for the mass spectra. One of the authors (ADG) is grateful to C,S,I,R, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. C. B. CLARKE 'A Review of the ferns of Northern India' Reprinted by B. SINGH, M. P. SINGH, Dehra Dun and Periodical Experts, Delhi, 1978, 550.
2. H. AGETA, K. IWATA and S. NATORI, *Tetrahedron letters*, 1963, 1447.
3. H. AGETA and K. IWATA, *Tetrahedron letters*, 1966, 6069.
4. H. AGETA, K. IWATA and S. NATORI, *Tetrahedron letters* 1964, 3413.
5. Y. TSUDA, K. ISOBE, S. FUKUSHIMA, H. AGETA and K. IWATA, *Tetrahedron letters*, 1967, 23.
6. H. AGETA, K. IWATA and K. YONEZAWA, *Chem. Pharm. Bull (Tokyo)*. 1968. 408.

Coumarins from *Pimpinella diversifolia*

CHANDER B. BHATIA, S. K. BANERJEE* and K. L. HANDA

Regional Research Laboratory, Jammu-Tawi-180001

Manuscript received 7 July 1977, revised 17 October 1977,

accepted 21 November 1977

P. diversifolia (Umbelliferae) is a herb growing in the north-western Himalayan region. No work on this plant has so far been reported. From the aerial parts of this plant two coumarins have been isolated and identified as ammirin (isoangonemalin) and oxypeucedanin on the basis of IR, NMR, MS and TLC data.

The petroleum ether extract of the air dried, powdered aerial parts (2 Kg) of the plant yielded a dark green residue (30 g) which was chromatographed over neutral alumina (grade IV). Elution with petroleum ether gave a mixture of hydrocarbons, m.p. 77-78°. The earlier benzene eluates on chromatography over silica gel followed by PLC afforded ammirin (44 mg) in needles (benzene-acetone), m.p. 110-12° (lit.², m.p. 117°), blue fluorescence under UV. NMR (90 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.79(3H, s, methyl), 3.27 (2H, dq, J 16, 8Hz, H-3'), 4.98(1H, br s) and 5.13 (1H, br s)-olefinic protons, 5.32 (1H, t, J 8Hz, H-2'), 6.23 (1H, d, J 9.5 Hz, H-3), 6.78 (1H, s, H-8), 7.30 (1H, s, H-5), 7.62 (1H, d, J 9.5 Hz, H-4). MS : Ion peaks at m/e 228 (M⁺), 213, 185 among others.

Later fractions of benzene eluates from silica gel chromatography, on purification by PLC, afforded oxypeucedanin (20 mg), m.p. 144-45° (lit.³ m.p. 142-43°), M⁺ 286. IR and NMR spectra were in concordance with those of an authentic sample.

Acknowledgement

We thank Dr. Sukh Dev of Malti Chem. Research Centre, Baroda for the NMR spectra.

References

1. E. A. ABU-MUSTAPHA, E. K. A. EL-BAY and M. B. E. FAYEZ, *Naturwissenschaften*, 1975, **62**, 39.
2. F. BOHLMANN, J. JACOB and M. GRENZ, *Chem. Ber.*, 1975, **108**, 433.
3. E. SPATH and K. KLAGER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1933, **66**, 914.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt with Furoin Thiosemicarbazone[®]

C. K. BHASKARE*, S. V. KULKARNI, K. N. GANAGE
and Mrs. SUREKHA DEVI

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416-004.
(India)

Manuscript received 11 January 1977, revised 4 August 1977,
accepted 21 November 1977

NUMEROUS reagents have been reported for the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt which include 1-nitroso-2 naphthol and thiocyanate¹, benzamidoxime², metidan³ and thioglycerol⁴. Recently thiosemicarbazones of picolinaldehyde⁵ and di-2 pyridylketone⁶ are reported as reagents for the determination of various metal ions such as cobalt, nickel, iron and copper. The reported methods either require elaborate experimental procedure or complexes are less stable in aqueous medium. In this paper we propose furoin thiosemicarbazone as a new spectrophotometric reagent which has considerably high stability in aqueous medium. The procedure is simple and the interference due to several ions may be easily removed.

Experimental

Reagent

Ethanollic 10% solution of furoin (5 m mole) and aqueous 20% solution of thiosemicarbazide (20 m mole) were mixed in presence of 2-3 drops of anhydrous acetic acid and refluxed for two hours. The yellowish crystals of furoin thiosemicarbazone appeared on cooling were recrystallized twice from hot (1 : 1) ethanol.

0.25% (w/v) solution of furoin thiosemicarbazone was prepared in (1 : 1) methanol. The reagent solution is stable for at least two months.

Cobalt solution

A stock solution (1 mg ml⁻¹) of cobalt(II) ion was prepared by dissolving cobalt sulphate heptahydrate in double distilled water and was standardized gravimetrically⁷.

[®] Paper presented to the Annual Convention of Chemists, Bangalore 1976.

Reagent grade chemicals were used throughout.

Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched glass cuvettes was used for measuring the absorbance. pH was monitored with Philips PR 9405L pH meter with glass and calomel electrodes. pH values of the solutions were adjusted by dil. hydrochloric acid or ammonia solutions.

General procedure

An aliquot of sample solution containing up to 10 ppm of cobalt was taken and excess (20 times) reagent was added. The pH was adjusted to 7.5 and the solution was diluted to 25 ml in standard flask with distilled water. The optical density of the cobalt complex was measured at 365 nm against reagent blank prepared in the same manner excluding cobalt. The concentration of cobalt in the unknown solution was found out from standard calibration curve obtained under identical conditions.

Results and Discussion

Investigation of the spectra

The spectra of furoin thiosemicarbazone : cobalt systems were run over a wide range of pH values which show an absorption band with $\lambda_{\max}$ at 365 nm. The extinction coefficient at 365 nm and at pH 7.5 is 8095 l mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of the Co(II)—Complex(B), and the ligand (A)

(B): Co(II) : $6.792 \times 10^{-5} M$ and ligand : $6.887 \times 10^{-3} M$
(A): Ligand : $6.887 \times 10^{-3} M$